

Rutherford Scattering: a comparison between Classical Mechanics, Non-Relativistic Quantum Mechanics, and Quantum Field Theory

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This is a review article that investigates the three approaches to Rutherford Scattering Theory - Classical Mechanics, Non-Relativistic Quantum Mechanics, and Quantum Field Theory - and their distinctions. In the first sections, the mathematical models are demonstrated and a qualitative analysis of the main differences in each interpretation of the phenomenon is performed. Next, numerical simulations show the effects of dealing with relativistic or non-relativistic limits. The results make it clear that no theory is essentially wrong, but the newer ones are just more complete and consider more relevant parameters.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the development of new theories allows us to better understand the mechanisms of physical systems. Previously unknown details become properly defined and we can make new predictions about the phenomena. In particular, a great example to illustrate this is the Rutherford Scattering and its different approaches that emerged with time.

Firstly, particle scattering is the phenomenon where moving objects are forced to deviate from their initial trajectory due to an interaction with another. Specifically, in 1909, Hans Geiger and Ernest Marsden conducted an experiment under supervision of Ernest Rutherford: it consists in bombarding a beam of α -particles towards a thin gold foil. Analyzing the results, they realized that the deflection occurred due to the electrostatic force. The mathematical modelling was done using a classical approach - Central Forces, basic geometry etc.

Later in that century, with the emerge of Quantum Mechanics, there was necessary to adapt the scattering model to the new concepts, so the mathematics followed a Non-Relativistic Quantum approach: Dirac picture of Schrödinger Equation, Time-dependent Perturbation Theory, Linear Algebra, Born Series etc.

However, in 1928, Paul Dirac combined the Quantum Theory with Special Relativity to take into account the relativistic corrections for fermions. This approach and its mathematical predictions were combined into the Quantum Electrodynamics.

Our goal is to compare these approaches and show that each new theory that emerged with time considers more parameters and yields different - but more complete - results.

II. THEORY

Classical Mechanics

The scattering theory deals with central forces (i.e. a force that points radially and whose magnitude depends only on the distance from the source) that follow the property

$$\mathbf{F} = -\nabla V(r) \quad (1)$$

where $V(r)$ is the scalar potential that depends only on the distance from the source.

The Lagrangian of a system where two particles interact due to a central force is

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2}m(\dot{r}^2 + r^2\dot{\theta}^2) - V(r), \quad (2)$$

and the equations of motion are

$$m(\ddot{r} - r\dot{\theta}^2) - V'(r) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(mr^2\dot{\theta}) = 0 \quad (4)$$

Note that Eq.(4) is just the conservation of angular momentum. Therefore, rewriting the angular velocity as $\dot{\theta} = \frac{L}{mr^2}$, Eq.(3) becomes

$$m\ddot{r} = \frac{L^2}{mr^3} - V'(r) \quad (5)$$

Multiplying both sides by \dot{r} and then integrating with respect to time, we have an expression that represents the total energy of the system:

$$\frac{1}{2}m\dot{r}^2 + V(r) + \frac{L^2}{2mr^2} = E \quad (6)$$

Isolating \dot{r} we have:

$$\dot{r} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{2}{m}(E - V(r)) - \frac{L^2}{m^2 r^2}} \quad (7)$$

We can use this expression when defining the rate of change of angle $\Theta(r)$ (see in FIG.1):

$$\begin{aligned} d\Theta &= \frac{d\Theta}{dt} \frac{dt}{dr} dr \\ \therefore d\Theta &= \frac{\dot{\Theta}}{\dot{r}} dr \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Replacing the expressions and solving the differential equation:

$$\Theta = \int \frac{\pm (L/r^2)}{\sqrt{2m(E - V - \frac{L^2}{2mr^2})}} dr \quad (9)$$

This integral must be evaluated using the limits r_{min} and ∞ , because we are interested in the interval between the closest approximation and the position where the deflected particle returned to a straight trajectory (free of central-force field). Also, we can use $L = b\sqrt{2mT_0}$ (where $T_0 = \frac{1}{2}mv_0^2$ is the energy free of central-force field) to write

$$\Theta = \int_{r_{min}}^{\infty} \frac{b/r^2}{\sqrt{1 - (b^2/r^2) - (V/T_0)}} dr \quad (10)$$

Finally, writing the potential for the Rutherford Scattering as

$$V(r) = \frac{k}{r} \quad (11)$$

where $k = q_1 q_2 / 4\pi\epsilon_0$, the integral takes the form

$$\Theta(r) = \int_{r_{min}}^{\infty} \frac{(b/r)}{\sqrt{r^2 - (k/T_0)r - b^2}} dr \quad (12)$$

Solving it gives us

$$\cos\Theta = \frac{(\kappa/b)}{\sqrt{1 + (\kappa/b)^2}} \quad (13)$$

where $\kappa = k/2T_0$. Since $\Theta = \pi/2 - \theta/2$, this equation yields:

$$b = \kappa \cot(\theta/2) \quad (14)$$

Now, consider a narrow beam of particles, each having charge q_1 and energy T_0 , directed towards a collection of particles with charge q_2 at rest. We define the **intensity** I as the number of particles passing in unit time through a unit area normal to the direction of the beam. If we assume that the interaction between charges q_1 and q_2 falls off with distance sufficiently rapidly, the motion of

FIG. 1: The trajectory of an object being deflected by the interaction with another. The point O represents the closest approximation between the two particles and b is the impact parameter.

a scattered particle asymptotically approaches a straight line with a well-defined angle θ . We now define a **differential cross section** $D(\theta)$ for the scattering - into an element of solid angle $d\Omega$ - as a measure of probability that the beam will be deflected by an angle θ , given by

$$D(\theta) = \frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{1}{I} \frac{dN}{d\Omega} \quad (15)$$

where $d\sigma$ is the infinitesimal cross-section area and dN is the number of particles dispersed into $d\Omega$ per unit time.

Since the scattering has axial symmetry, we perform the integration in $d\Omega$ over the whole interval of azimuthal angle. Then:

$$d\Omega = 2\pi \sin\theta d\theta \quad (16)$$

FIG. 2: A beam of particles being scattered.

Take a look at FIG.2 and see that the number of particles with impact parameter within a range db at a distance b must correspond to the number of particles scattered into the angular range $d\theta$ at an angle θ . Thus, we can write

$$I \cdot 2\pi b db = -I \cdot D(\theta) \cdot 2\pi \sin\theta d\theta \quad (17)$$

where $db/d\theta$ is negative, because we assume that the amount of angular deflection decreases (monotonically)

with increasing impact parameter. Therefore:

$$D(\theta) = \frac{b}{\sin\theta} \left| \frac{db}{d\theta} \right| \quad (18)$$

Using the definition from Eq.(14), it is easy to see that

$$\frac{db}{d\theta} = -\frac{\kappa}{2} \frac{1}{\sin^2(\theta/2)}, \quad (19)$$

and then

$$D(\theta) = \frac{\kappa^2}{2} \frac{\cot(\theta/2)}{\sin\theta \sin^2(\theta/2)} \quad (20)$$

Once we know that $\sin\theta = 2\sin(\theta/2)\cos(\theta/2)$ the equation turns to:

$$D(\theta) = \frac{\kappa^2}{4} \frac{1}{\sin^4(\theta/2)}, \quad (21)$$

and finally,

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{k^2}{(4T_0)^2} \frac{1}{\sin^4(\theta/2)} = \left[\frac{q_1 q_2}{16\pi\epsilon_0 T_0 \sin^2(\theta/2)} \right]^2 \quad (22)$$

from the definitions of κ and $D(\theta)$.

Note that it is independent of the sign of k , so that the form of the scattering distribution is the same for repulsive or attractive forces. Also, if v_0 is small, we see that $D(\theta)$ increases, that is, if the beam has a large area it gets deflected nearly straight backward.

In addition, if we want to find the **total cross-section**, we can perform:

$$\sigma_t \equiv \int \left[\frac{q_1 q_2}{16\pi\epsilon_0 T_0 \sin^2(\theta/2)} \right]^2 d\Omega \quad (23)$$

Our work is finally done (or maybe not). Given the impact parameter, we are able to predict the differential cross section (until the beginning of twentieth century, this classical approach was even useful). However, at that point, the new concepts developed by Modern Physics showed us that the universe is uncertain on microscopic scales. Hence, an important question arises: **would our classical theory change when introducing these new definitions?** The Rutherford Scattering deals with alpha particles and gold atoms, therefore, it seems appropriate to use the Quantum Mechanics formalism.

Non-Relativistic Quantum Mechanics

We shall start considering the scattering phenomenon as a time-dependent perturbation, that is, a continuum initial state of the particles is transformed into a continuum final state, through the action of some potential.

To represent the evolution of a state into another, we write

$$|\psi, t; t_0\rangle_I = U_I(t, t_0) |\psi, t_0; t_0\rangle_I, \quad (24)$$

where $U_I(t, t_0)$ satisfies the equation

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} U_I(t, t_0) = V_I(t) U_I(t, t_0) \quad (25)$$

(The subscript I represents the Interaction/Dirac picture.)

The solution of Eq.(25) is the well-known Dyson Series (we will use only the first order):

$$U_I(t, t_0) = 1 + \frac{(-i)}{\hbar} \int_{t_0}^t V_I(t') U_I(t', t_0) dt' \quad (26)$$

Therefore, using the completeness relation, the "transition amplitude" for an initial state $|i\rangle$ to transform into a final state $|n\rangle$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n | U_I(t, t_0) | i \rangle &= \delta_{ni} + \frac{(-i)}{\hbar} \sum_m \langle n | V | i \rangle \\ &+ \int_{t_0}^t e^{i\omega_{nm}} \langle n | U_I(t', t_0) | i \rangle dt' \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Once both initial and final states exist only asymptotically, we set $\langle n | U_I(t', t_0) | i \rangle = \delta_{k'k}$ over the limits $-\infty$ and ∞ :

$$\langle n | U_I(t, t_0) | i \rangle = \delta_{ni} + \frac{(-i)}{\hbar} \langle n | V | i \rangle \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\omega_{ni}t'} dt' \quad (28)$$

In this case, as $t \rightarrow \infty$ we see a "transition rate" emerge as Fermi's golden rule:

$$w(i \rightarrow n) = \left(\frac{2\pi}{\hbar} \right) |V_{ni}|^2 \delta(E_n - E_i) \quad (29)$$

Hence, in order to also accommodate $t_0 \rightarrow -\infty$, we define a matrix T as follows:

$$\langle n | U_I(t, t_0) | i \rangle = \delta_{ni} + \frac{(-i)}{\hbar} T_{ni} \int_{t_0}^t e^{i\omega_{ni}t' + \epsilon t'} dt' \quad (30)$$

where $\epsilon > 0$ and $t \ll (1/\epsilon)$. These conditions ensure that $e^{\epsilon t'}$ is close to unity as $t \rightarrow \infty$ and that the integrand goes to zero as $t_0 \rightarrow \infty$. We just need to make sure that we take the limit $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ first, before we take $t \rightarrow +\infty$.

We can now define the scattering (or S) matrix

$$\begin{aligned} S_{ni} &\equiv \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left[\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle n | U_I(t, -\infty) | i \rangle \right] \\ &= \delta_{ni} + \frac{(-i)}{\hbar} T_{ni} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\omega_{ni}t'} dt', \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

and evaluate the integral to obtain:

$$S_{ni} = \delta_{ni} - 2\pi i \delta(E_n - E_i) T_{ni} \quad (32)$$

Clearly, the S matrix consists of two parts. One part is that in which the final state is the same as the initial state. The second part, governed by the T matrix, is one in which some sort of scattering occurs.

Proceeding, we define the transition rate as

$$w(i \rightarrow n) = \frac{d}{dt} |\langle n | U_I(t, -\infty) | i \rangle|^2, \quad (33)$$

where for $|i\rangle \neq |n\rangle$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n | U_I(t, -\infty) | i \rangle &= -\frac{i}{\hbar} T_{ni} \int_{-\infty}^t e^{i\omega_{ni}t' + \epsilon t'} dt' \\ &= -\frac{i}{\hbar} T_{ni} \frac{e^{i\omega_{ni}t + \epsilon t}}{i\omega_{ni} + \epsilon} \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} w(i \rightarrow n) &= \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{1}{\hbar^2} |T_{ni}|^2 \frac{e^{2\epsilon t}}{\omega_{ni}^2 + \epsilon^2} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{\hbar^2} |T_{ni}|^2 \frac{2\epsilon e^{2\epsilon t}}{\omega_{ni}^2 + \epsilon^2} \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

We need to take $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ for finite values of t , and then $t \rightarrow \infty$. Clearly this will send $w \rightarrow 0$ if $\omega_{ni} \neq 0$, so we see something like $\delta(\omega_{ni})$ emerging, which is not unexpected given EQ.(32). In fact, because

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\omega_{ni}^2 + \epsilon^2} d\omega = \frac{\pi}{\epsilon} \quad (36)$$

for $\epsilon > 0$, we have, for finite t ,

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{2\epsilon e^{2\epsilon t}}{\omega_{ni}^2 + \epsilon^2} = \pi \delta(\omega_{ni}) = \pi \hbar \delta(E_n - E_i) \quad (37)$$

which is independent of time, so the limit as $t \rightarrow \infty$ is trivial. This expression is strikingly similar to Fermi's golden rule (Eq.(29)), except that V_{ni} has been replaced by the more general T_{ni} . We will see below how to determine the matrix elements T_{ni} in general. First, however, let us continue with this discussion and use the transition rate to express the scattering cross section.

First, there is the normalization of the initial and final states. Eq.(27) assumes discrete states, but our scattering states are in the continuum, this is why we shall normalize them in a "big box". In the coordinate representation, we write

$$\langle \mathbf{x} | \mathbf{k} \rangle = \frac{1}{L^{3/2}} e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} \quad (38)$$

in which case $\langle \mathbf{k}' | \mathbf{k} \rangle = \delta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$, where the \mathbf{k} take on discrete values. We will take $L \rightarrow \infty$ at the end of any calculation.

Then, in order to integrate over the final-state energy E_n , we need to determine the density of final states $\rho(E_n) = \Delta n / \Delta E_n$. We will determine the density of

states for elastic scattering, where $|i\rangle = |\mathbf{k}\rangle$ and $|n\rangle = |\mathbf{k}'\rangle$ and $|\mathbf{k}| = |\mathbf{k}'| \equiv k$. The normalization yields

$$E_{\mathbf{k}'} = \frac{\hbar^2 \mathbf{k}'^2}{2m} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{2\pi}{L} \right)^2 |\mathbf{k}'|^2 \quad (39)$$

where $\mathbf{k}' = k'_x \hat{\mathbf{x}} + k'_y \hat{\mathbf{y}} + k'_z \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ and $k'_{x,y,z} \in \mathbb{Z}$. Consequently

$$\Delta E_{\mathbf{k}'} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{2\pi}{L} \right)^2 |\mathbf{k}'| \Delta |\mathbf{k}'| \quad (40)$$

Note that because $\mathbf{k}' \equiv (L/2\pi)\mathbf{k}$ and L is large, we can think of $|\mathbf{k}'|$ as nearly continuous, and the number of states within a spherical shell of radius $|\mathbf{k}'|$ and thickness $\Delta |\mathbf{k}'|$ is

$$\Delta = 4\pi |\mathbf{k}'|^2 \Delta |\mathbf{k}'| \times \frac{d\Omega}{4\pi} \quad (41)$$

taking into account the fraction of solid angle represented by the final-state wave vector \mathbf{k}' . Therefore,

$$\rho(E_{\mathbf{k}'}) = \frac{m}{\hbar^2} \left(\frac{L}{2\pi} \right)^2 |\mathbf{k}'| d\Omega = \frac{mk}{\hbar^2} \left(\frac{L}{2\pi} \right)^3 d\Omega \quad (42)$$

and after integrating over final states, the transition rate is given by

$$w(\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}') = \frac{mkL^3}{(2\pi)^2 \hbar^3} |T_{\mathbf{k}'\mathbf{k}}|^2 d\Omega \quad (43)$$

We use the concept of cross section to interpret the transition rate in scattering experiments. That is, we determine the rate at which particles are scattered into a solid angle $d\Omega$ from a "beam" of particles with momentum $\hbar\mathbf{k}$. The speed of these particles is $v = \hbar k/m$, so the time it takes for a particle to cross the "big box" is L/v . Thus the flux in the particle beam is $(1/L^2) \div (L/v) = v/L^3$. This way, we can define the *probability flux* $\mathbf{j}(\mathbf{x}, t) = (\hbar/m) \cdot \text{Im}(\psi^* \nabla \psi)$ for the wave function $\langle \mathbf{x} | \mathbf{k} \rangle$:

$$\mathbf{j}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \left(\frac{\hbar}{m} \right) \frac{\mathbf{k}}{L^3} = \frac{v}{L^3} \quad (44)$$

Since the differential cross section $d\sigma/d\Omega$ is simply defined as the transition rate divided by the flux, we finally obtain:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \left(\frac{mL^3}{2\pi\hbar^2} \right)^2 |T_{\mathbf{k}'\mathbf{k}}|^2 \quad (45)$$

Now we must solve the Eq.(34) for the T matrix. Rewriting it gives

$$\langle \mathbf{k}' | U_I(t, -\infty) | \mathbf{k} \rangle = \delta_{\mathbf{k}'\mathbf{k}} + \frac{1}{\hbar} T_{\mathbf{k}'\mathbf{k}} \frac{e^{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}'\mathbf{k}}t + \epsilon t}}{-\omega_{\mathbf{k}'\mathbf{k}} + \epsilon} \quad (46)$$

that we will replace into Eq.(27). This results in three terms: the first is $\delta_{k'k}$, and the second looks just like Eq.(46) but with $T_{k'k}$ replaced with $V_{k'm}$. The third term is (writing $\langle \mathbf{k}' | V | m \rangle$ as $V_{k'm}$):

$$-\frac{i}{\hbar} \frac{1}{\hbar} \sum_m V_{k'm} \frac{T_{mk}}{-\omega_{mk} + i\epsilon} \int_{-\infty}^t e^{i\omega_{k'm}t' + i\omega_{mk}t' + \epsilon t'} dt' \quad (47)$$

The integral is then carried out, and since $\omega_{k'm} + \omega_{mk} = \omega_{k'k}$, the result can be taken outside the summation. Gathering terms and comparing the result to Eq.(46), we discover the following relation:

$$T_{k'k} = V_{k'k} + \sum_m V_{k'm} \frac{T_{mk}}{E_k - E_{k'} + i\hbar\epsilon} \quad (48)$$

This is an inhomogeneous system of linear equations that can be solved for the values $T_{k'k}$, in terms of the known matrix elements $V_{k'm}$. It is convenient to define a set of vectors $|\psi^{(+)}\rangle$ in terms of components in some basis $|q\rangle$, so that

$$T_{k'k} = \sum_q \langle \mathbf{k}' | V | q \rangle \langle q | \psi^{(+)} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{k}' | V | \psi^{(+)} \rangle \quad (49)$$

Back to Eq.(45):

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \left(\frac{mL^3}{2\pi\hbar^2} \right)^2 |\langle \mathbf{k}' | V | \psi^{(+)} \rangle|^2 \quad (50)$$

The states $|\psi^{(+)}\rangle$ are the wave functions of the whole system at an infinite time before the interaction. They are properly defined by the well-known **Lippmann-Schwinger Equation**:

$$|\psi^{(+)}\rangle = |\mathbf{k}\rangle + \frac{1}{E_k - H^{(0)} + i\epsilon} V |\psi^{(+)}\rangle \quad (51)$$

where $H^{(0)}$ is the Hamiltonian that describes the situation free of interaction.

Note that we have introduced the matrix elements $T_{k'k}$ simply as complex numbers. However, we can also define an operator T whose matrix elements $\langle \mathbf{k}' | T | \mathbf{k} \rangle = T_{k'k}$ by writing $T |\mathbf{k}\rangle = V |\psi^{(+)}\rangle$, then, operating on Eq.(51) with V from the left leads to the following operator equation:

$$T = V + V \frac{1}{E_k - H^{(0)} + i\epsilon} V + V \frac{1}{E_k - H^{(0)} + i\epsilon} V \frac{1}{E_k - H^{(0)} + i\epsilon} V + \dots \quad (52)$$

Therefore, the expression for the differential cross section turns to:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \left(\frac{mL^3}{2\pi\hbar^2} \right)^2 |\langle \mathbf{k}' | T | \mathbf{k} \rangle|^2 \quad (53)$$

Now, we need to find expressions for

There is something else that will be useful: the *scattering amplitude* $f(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})$. It tells us the probability of scattering in a given direction, and hence is related to the differential cross-section. Indeed, the probability that the incident particle, traveling at speed v , passes through the infinitesimal area $d\sigma$, in time dt , is (see FIG.3)

$$dP = |\psi_{incident}|^2 dV = |A|^2 (v dt) d\sigma \quad (54)$$

FIG. 3: The volume dV of incident beam that passes through area $d\sigma$ in time dt .

But this is equal to the probability that the particle later emerges into the corresponding solid angle $d\Omega$:

$$|\psi_{incident}|^2 dV = \frac{|A|^2 |f|^2}{r^2} r^2 (v dt) d\Omega \quad (55)$$

from which it follows that

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = |f(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})|^2 \quad (56)$$

and, consequently (using Eq.(50))

$$|f(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| = \frac{mL^3}{2\pi\hbar^2} \langle \mathbf{k}' | T | \mathbf{k} \rangle \quad (57)$$

From here, we will start working on approximations of T . Let us first take $T = V$ (the first-order, also known as **Born Approximation**). Using the completeness relation, we obtain:

$$|f^{(1)}(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| = \frac{mL^3}{2\pi\hbar^2} \int d^3x' \langle \mathbf{k}' | \mathbf{x}' \rangle \langle \mathbf{x}' | \mathbf{k} \rangle V(\mathbf{x}') \quad (58)$$

Now we need to define the expressions for $\langle \mathbf{x}' | \mathbf{k} \rangle$ and $\langle \mathbf{k}' | \mathbf{x}' \rangle$. From the definition of Eq.(38), we write:

$$\langle \mathbf{x}' | \mathbf{k} \rangle = \frac{e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}'}}{L^{3/2}} \quad (59)$$

and

$$\langle \mathbf{k}' | \mathbf{x}' \rangle = \frac{e^{-i\mathbf{k}'\cdot\mathbf{x}'}}{L^{3/2}} \quad (60)$$

Finally, replacing these two expressions into Eq.(58):

$$|f(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| = \frac{m}{2\pi\hbar^2} \int d^3x' e^{i(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}')\cdot\mathbf{x}'} V(\mathbf{x}') \quad (61)$$

Now, if we define $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = \mathbf{k}' - \mathbf{k}$ (see FIG.4), we can perform an angular integration explicitly to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |f^{(1)}(\theta)| &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} \frac{1}{\kappa} \int_0^\infty \frac{r^2}{r} V(r) (e^{i\kappa r} - e^{-i\kappa r}) dr \\ &= \frac{2m}{\hbar^2 \kappa} \int_0^\infty r V(r) \sin(\kappa r) dr, \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

since $\kappa = 2k \sin(\theta/2)$.

FIG. 4: First-order scattering through angle θ .

Now we shall introduce the **Yukawa potential**, which is a crude model for the binding force in an atomic nucleus. It has the form

$$V(r) = \beta \frac{e^{-\mu r}}{r} \quad (63)$$

where β and μ are constants. Plugging it into Eq.(63), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} |f^{(1)}(\theta)| &= \frac{2m\beta}{\hbar^2 \kappa} \int_0^\infty e^{-\mu r} \sin(\kappa r) dr \\ &= \frac{2m\beta}{\hbar^2(\mu^2 + \kappa^2)} \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

It is useful because the **Coulomb potential** (that describes the Rutherford Scattering) can be obtained by putting $\beta = q_1 q_2 / 4\pi\epsilon_0$ and $\mu = 0$ into Eq.(64). Therefore, the absolute value of the first-order amplitude can be expressed as

$$|f^{(1)}(\theta)| = \frac{2mq_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2 \kappa^2} \quad (65)$$

From the **Helmholtz Equation** $\left[(\nabla^2 + k^2) G_+(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \delta^{(3)}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') \right]$, we obtain $k = \sqrt{2mT_0}/\hbar$. Plugging it into the definition of κ , our equation turns to

$$|f^{(1)}(\theta)| = \frac{q_1 q_2}{16\pi\epsilon_0 T_0 \sin^2(\theta/2)}, \quad (66)$$

and we finally use Eq.(56) to write:

$$D^{(1)}(\theta) = \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)^{(1)} = \left[\frac{q_1 q_2}{16\pi\epsilon_0 T_0 \sin^2(\theta/2)} \right]^2 \quad (67)$$

Note that this is exactly the same equation as (22). Therefore, we conclude that the expression obtained by Classical Mechanics is just the first-order approximation of the real differential cross-section obtained by Quantum Mechanics. If we want to find a more exactly solution, we have to work with higher orders of the operator T . For example, the second-order approximation is:

$$|f(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| \approx |f^{(1)}(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| + |f^{(2)}(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| \quad (68)$$

where

$$|f^{(1)}(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| = \frac{q_1 q_2}{16\pi\epsilon_0 T_0 \sin^2(\theta/2)} \quad (69)$$

and

$$|f^{(2)}(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| = \frac{m}{2\pi\hbar^2} \left\langle \mathbf{k}' \left| V \frac{1}{E_k - H^{(0)} + i\epsilon} V \right| \mathbf{k} \right\rangle \quad (70)$$

We can use the completeness relation for \mathbf{x}' and \mathbf{x}'' to produce:

$$\begin{aligned} |f^{(2)}(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} \int d^3 x' \int d^3 x'' \langle \mathbf{k}' | \mathbf{x}' \rangle \\ &V(\mathbf{x}') \left[\frac{2m}{\hbar^2} G_+(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}'') \right] V(\mathbf{x}'') \langle \mathbf{x}'' | \mathbf{k} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

where the Green's Function can be expressed as

$$G_+(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}'') = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{e^{ik|\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x}''|}}{|\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x}''|}, \quad (72)$$

and the potential

$$V(\mathbf{x}') = \frac{\beta}{x'} \quad \text{and} \quad V(\mathbf{x}'') = \frac{\beta}{x''} \quad (73)$$

Eq.(71) takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} |f^{(2)}(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{k})| &= \left[\frac{m\beta}{2\pi\hbar^2} \right]^2 \int d^3 x' \\ &\int d^3 x'' \frac{e^{-i\mathbf{k}' \cdot \mathbf{x}'}}{x'} \frac{e^{ik|\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x}''|}}{|\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x}''|} \frac{e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}''}}{x''} \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

From here, we could proceed by writing $d^3 \mathbf{x}'$ and $d^3 \mathbf{x}''$ in spherical coordinates and opening the scalar products in the exponents. This would allow us to find an expression for the second-order amplitude $|f^{(2)}(\theta)|$ and solve Eq.(68).

The main purpose of dealing with Quantum Mechanics can be identified here: if we were to calculate higher orders of the scattering amplitude, we would realize that each term has a position and an associated potential.

This means that there are infinite virtual states between $|\mathbf{k}\rangle$ and $|\mathbf{k}'\rangle$ that describe the position of the particle at each point of the trajectory. Classical Mechanics fails to describe this intermediate behavior of the scattering between the initial and final states (see FIG.5), on other hand, Quantum Mechanics takes into account that the particle undergoes successive deflections at each infinitesimal propagation (see FIG.7).

FIG. 5: Physical interpretation of the classical mechanics approach (first-order scattering amplitude).

FIG. 6: Physical interpretation of the second-order amplitude.

FIG. 7: Physical interpretation of the superior-orders amplitude; higher the orders, more precise is the prediction.

We are done with the Non-Relativistic Quantum Mechanics! We found out a way to describe the Rutherford Scattering as a whole, taking into account the various

virtual transitions between the initial and final states. However, there is still one more thing to do: relativistic corrections! Since we are dealing with α -particles and atoms that move close to the speed of light, we know from Special Relativity that there will be considerable differences.

Quantum Field Theory

In the classical mechanics section, we analyzed how the trajectory of a charge q_1 is deflected when approaching another charge q_2 . In the non-relativistic quantum mechanics section, a more detailed discussion on the scattering of a plane wave due to a Coulomb potential was made. Now, we will investigate the Rutherford scattering with relativistic corrections, based on Quantum Field Theory (QFT).

First, let us determine an expression for the infinitesimal scattering cross section $d\sigma$ described by a probability. Consider a target composed of N_A particles of type A and an incident beam containing N_B particles of type B . Thus, the total number N of scattering events relative to $d\sigma$ is given by:

$$N = (\text{event probability}) \cdot N_B = \left(\frac{N_A d\sigma}{A} \right) N_B$$

where A is the common area to the target and the incident beam. Defining n_B as the number of particles B per unit area, we have:

$$N = N_A n_B d\sigma \Rightarrow d\sigma = \frac{N}{N_A n_B}$$

We can also compute N from n_B and the scattering probability $P(\mathbf{b})$ which depends on the impact parameter \mathbf{b} (Fig. 8). Thus, considering n_B uniform in the interaction range, we have for one target particle:

$$d\sigma = \frac{N}{N_A n_B} = \frac{\int d^2b n_B P(\mathbf{b})}{1 \cdot n_B} = \int d^2b P(\mathbf{b})$$

FIG. 8: The incident beam approaching the target particle.

Now, let us find $d\sigma$ by computing $P(\mathbf{b})$ and performing the integration above. Asymptotically defining the initial state of the particles $|\psi\rangle_{in}$ in the remote past and the final state $|p\rangle_{out}$ in the far future, the probability for the *in state* $|\psi\rangle_{in}$ scatter into the *out state* $|p\rangle_{out}$ is given by:

$$P(\mathbf{b}) = \frac{d^3p}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{2E_p} |\langle p | \psi \rangle_{out}|^2 \quad (75)$$

$$= \frac{d^3p}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{2E_p} \langle p | \psi \rangle_{out} \langle p | \psi \rangle_{in}^* \quad (76)$$

where the energy term $2E_p$ comes from relativistic normalization. We can express the in state with a definite momentum \mathbf{k} as

$$|\psi\rangle = \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2E_k}} \phi(\mathbf{k}) e^{-i\mathbf{b}\cdot\mathbf{k}} |\mathbf{k}\rangle$$

Using this expression into Eq.(76), we get:

$$P(\mathbf{b}) = \frac{d^3p}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{2E_p} \int \frac{d^3k d^3k'}{(2\pi)^6} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2E_k 2E_{k'}}} \phi(\mathbf{k}) \phi^*(\mathbf{k}') e^{-i\mathbf{b}\cdot(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}')} \langle p | k \rangle_{out} \langle p | k' \rangle_{in}^* \quad (77)$$

where k' indicates the momentum for the complex-conjugated part. We have used so far the Heisenberg picture to represent the states. Since the in and out states are asymptotically defined ($t \rightarrow \infty$), we can write them in the Schrodinger picture as:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle p | k \rangle_{out} &= \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle p | e^{-iHt} e^{iH(-t)} | k \rangle \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle p | e^{-iH(2t)} | k \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Observing this connection between states, we recall the *S-matrix*, which determines the evolution of a state from a remote past ($t = -\infty$) to a far future ($t = \infty$):

$$\langle p | k \rangle_{out} \equiv \langle p | S | k \rangle$$

If the particles do not interact, there is no scattering and the S-matrix is the identity matrix. Since we are interested in scattering events, we divide the S-matrix in two parts:

$$S \equiv 1 + iT$$

where iT is the interacting part. Now, we can compute the brackets from Eq.(77) regarding only the scattering events:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle p | k \rangle_{out} &= \langle p | iT | k \rangle \\ \langle p | k' \rangle_{in}^* &= \langle p | iT | k' \rangle^* \end{aligned}$$

Let us rewrite the equations above as:

$$\langle p | iT | k \rangle = (2\pi)\delta(E_p - E_k) \cdot i\mathcal{M}(k \rightarrow p) \quad (78)$$

$$\langle p | iT | k' \rangle^* = -(2\pi)\delta(E_p - E_{k'}) \cdot i\mathcal{M}^*(k' \rightarrow p) \quad (79)$$

The term \mathcal{M} is called *invariant matrix element* and it is analogous to the scattering amplitude of the non-relativistic quantum case, as we will check later. The delta functions are due to the conservation of energy. Substituting Eq.(79) and Eq.(78) into Eq.(77), we get:

$$P(\mathbf{b}) = \frac{d^3p}{2E_p} \int \frac{d^3k d^3k'}{(2\pi)^7 \sqrt{2E_k 2E_{k'}}} \phi(\mathbf{k}) \phi^*(\mathbf{k}') e^{-i\mathbf{b}\cdot(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{M}(k \rightarrow p) \mathcal{M}^*(k' \rightarrow p) \delta(E_p - E_{k'}) \delta(E_p - E_k) \quad (80)$$

Therefore, the differential scattering cross section is:

$$d\sigma = \frac{d^3p}{2E_p} \int \frac{d^2b d^3k d^3k'}{(2\pi)^7 \sqrt{2E_k 2E_{k'}}} \phi(\mathbf{k}) \phi^*(\mathbf{k}') e^{-i\mathbf{b}\cdot(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}')} \mathcal{M}(k \rightarrow p) \mathcal{M}^*(k' \rightarrow p) \delta(E_p - E_{k'}) \delta(E_p - E_k) \quad (81)$$

First, we integrate over b :

$$\int d^2b e^{-i\mathbf{b}\cdot(\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{k}')} = (2\pi)^2 \delta^{(2)}(k_\perp - k'_\perp) \quad (82)$$

Now, we rewrite $\delta(E_p - E_k)$ using the identity $\delta(f(x) - f(x_0)) = \frac{1}{f'(x_0)} \delta(x - x_0)$:

$$\delta(E_p - E_k) = \frac{E_k}{k_z} \delta(k_z - k'_z) = \frac{1}{v} \delta(k_z - k'_z)$$

where v is the velocity of the incident particles. These delta functions in the scattering cross section forces together $k = k'$. Therefore, the integral over k' (using the components of $d^3k' = d^2k'_\perp dk'_z$) is:

$$\begin{aligned} \int d^2k'_\perp dk'_z \frac{\phi^*(\mathbf{k}') \mathcal{M}^*(k' \rightarrow p)}{v \sqrt{2E_{k'}}} (2\pi)^2 \delta^{(2)}(k_\perp - k'_\perp) \delta(k_z - k'_z) \\ = \frac{(2\pi)^2 \phi^*(\mathbf{k}) \mathcal{M}^*(k \rightarrow p)}{v \sqrt{2E_k}} \end{aligned} \quad (83)$$

Thus, we can perform the integration over k and calculate $d\sigma$:

$$\begin{aligned} d\sigma &= \frac{d^3p}{2E_p} \int \frac{d^3k}{v(2\pi)^5 2E_k} |\phi(\mathbf{k})|^2 |\mathcal{M}(k \rightarrow p)|^2 \delta(E_p - E_k) \\ &= \frac{d^3p}{2E_p} \frac{1}{v(2\pi)^2 2E_k} |\mathcal{M}(k \rightarrow p)|^2 \delta(E_p - E_k) \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} |\phi(\mathbf{k})|^2 \end{aligned}$$

Recalling the normalization

$$\int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} |\phi(\mathbf{k})|^2 = 1$$

we find:

$$d\sigma = \frac{d^3p}{2E_p} \frac{1}{v(2\pi)^2 2E_k} |\mathcal{M}(k \rightarrow p)|^2 \delta(E_p - E_k)$$

In spherical coordinates, we have $d^3p = p^2 dp d\Omega$, so:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} &= \int \frac{p^2 dp}{2E_p} \frac{1}{v(2\pi)^2 2E_k} |\mathcal{M}|^2 \delta(E_p - E_k) \\ &= \frac{1}{(4\pi)^2} \int dp \frac{1}{v} \frac{p^2}{E_p E_k} |\mathcal{M}|^2 \frac{1}{v} \delta(p - k) \\ &= \frac{1}{(4\pi)^2} \int dp \frac{1}{v^2} \frac{p^2}{E_p E_k} |\mathcal{M}|^2 \delta(p - k) \\ &= \frac{1}{(4\pi)^2} |\mathcal{M}|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

Note that, similarly to the scattering amplitude f of the non-relativistic quantum case, the computation of the invariant matrix element \mathcal{M} determines the differential cross section. To find this quantity, we use the Yukawa interaction Hamiltonian:

$$H_{int} = \int d^3x e\bar{\psi}\gamma^\mu\psi A_\mu$$

So that we evaluate:

$$\langle p | iT | k \rangle = \langle p | T \left\{ e^{-i \int dt H_{int}} \right\} | k \rangle$$

Based on the S-matrix expansion, we find to the first-order (the zeroth-order is assigned to the non-interacting part of the S-matrix):

$$\langle p | iT | k \rangle = \overbrace{\langle p | T \{ -i \int d^4x e\bar{\psi}\gamma^\mu\psi A_\mu \} | k \rangle}$$

$$\langle p | iT | k \rangle = -ie\bar{u}^s(p)\gamma^\mu u^r(k) \int d^4x e^{ip \cdot x} e^{-ik \cdot x} A_\mu$$

where $\bar{u}^s(p)$ and $u^r(k)$ are four component spinors from Dirac equation. The integral above is a Fourier transform that yields the potential in momentum space and a delta function of energy:

$$\langle p | iT | k \rangle = -ie\bar{u}(p)\gamma^\mu u(k) \tilde{A}_\mu(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}) (2\pi) \delta(E_p - E_k)$$

Combining the equation above and Eq. (78), we get:

$$\mathcal{M} = -e\bar{u}^s(p)\gamma^\mu u^r(k) \tilde{A}_\mu(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}) \quad (85)$$

Since the Rutherford scattering takes place by Coulomb interaction, the potential in the position space is given by:

$$A_0(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{Ze}{4\pi r}$$

And, in momentum space, the potential is

$$\tilde{A}_0(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}) = \frac{Ze}{|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}|^2} = \frac{Ze}{4k^2 \sin^2(\theta/2)} \quad (86)$$

Substituting Eq. (83) into Eq. (82), we get:

$$\mathcal{M} = -e\bar{u}^s(p)\gamma^\mu u^r(k) \frac{Ze}{4k^2 \sin^2(\theta/2)}$$

In order to obtain $|\mathcal{M}|^2$, we use the property

$$(\bar{u}^s(p)\gamma^\mu u^r(k))^* = \bar{u}^r(k)\gamma^\mu u^s(p)$$

then, we find:

$$|\mathcal{M}|^2 = \frac{Z^2 e^4}{16k^4 \sin^4(\theta/2)} \bar{u}^s(p)\gamma^\mu u^r(k) \bar{u}^r(k)\gamma^\nu u^s(p)$$

Considering the incident beam as unpolarized, we define \mathcal{M} averaging over the initial spin r and summing over the final spin s :

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{M}|^2 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{r,s} \frac{Z^2 e^4}{16k^4 \sin^4(\theta/2)} \bar{u}^s(p)\gamma^\mu u^r(k) \bar{u}^r(k)\gamma^\nu u^s(p) \\ &= \frac{Z^2 e^4}{32k^4 \sin^4(\theta/2)} \sum_{r,s} \bar{u}^s(p)\gamma^\mu u^r(k) \bar{u}^r(k)\gamma^\nu u^s(p) \end{aligned}$$

Using the relations

$$\sum_r u_\alpha^r(k) \bar{u}_\beta^r(k) = (\not{k} + m)_{\alpha\beta}$$

$$\sum_s u_{\alpha'}^s(p) \bar{u}_{\beta'}^s(p) = (\not{p} + m)_{\alpha'\beta'}$$

where $\not{k} \equiv k \cdot \gamma$ and $\not{p} \equiv p \cdot \gamma$, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{M}|^2 &= \frac{Z^2 e^4}{32k^4 \sin^4(\theta/2)} \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu (\not{p} + m) \gamma^\nu (\not{k} + m)) \\ &= \frac{Z^2 e^4}{32k^4 \sin^4(\theta/2)} [\text{tr}(\gamma^\mu \not{p} \gamma^\nu \not{k}) + \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu m \gamma^\nu \not{k}) \\ &\quad + \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu \not{p} \gamma^\nu m) + \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu m \gamma^\nu m)] \end{aligned}$$

Since the trace of any product of an odd number of gamma matrices is zero, this equation reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{M}|^2 &= \frac{Z^2 e^4}{32k^4 \sin^4(\theta/2)} [\text{tr}(\gamma^\mu \not{p} \gamma^\nu \not{k}) + \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu m \gamma^\nu m)] \\ &= \frac{Z^2 e^4}{32k^4 \sin^4(\theta/2)} \cdot 8 \frac{k^2}{v^2} (1 - v^2 \sin^2(\theta/2)) \\ &= \frac{Z^2 e^4 (1 - v^2 \sin^2(\theta/2))}{4k^2 v^2 \sin^4(\theta/2)}. \end{aligned}$$

Plugging it into Eq.(81), we obtain the *differential cross section for relativistic Rutherford scattering to the first-order*:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{Z^2 e^4 (1 - v^2 \sin^2(\theta/2))}{64\pi^2 k^2 v^2 \sin^4(\theta/2)}$$

This equation can be rewritten with the fine-structure constant $\alpha = e^2/4\pi \approx 1/137$ as

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{Z^2 \alpha^2 (1 - v^2 \sin^2(\theta/2))}{4k^2 v^2 \sin^4(\theta/2)}$$

If we take the non-relativistic limit, then $k \approx mv$ and $1 - v^2 \sin^2(\theta/2) \approx 1$. Hence, the differential cross section becomes

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{Z^2 \alpha^2}{4m^2 v^4 \sin^4(\theta/2)}$$

which is precisely the same as Eq.(22), with $q_1 = e$ and $q_2 = Ze$. Thus, we conclude that the classical formula is a first-order result from the differential cross section obtained from Quantum Field Theory **in addition to non-relativistic approximations**.

We have used Planck units and $q_1 = e$ in this section. By modifying Yukawa's interaction Hamiltonian and writing the differential cross section in general, we get:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{q_1^2 q_2^2}{64\pi^2 \epsilon_0^2 k^2 v^2 \sin^4(\theta/2)} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \sin^2(\theta/2) \right)$$

III. COMPARING RESULTS

We have quantitatively described the Rutherford scattering from three approaches. The results obtained in Classical Mechanics and the first order term in Non-Relativistic Quantum Mechanics are identical, yet the qualitative differences between these theories have already been discussed. However, the first order term in the QFT section is different from the Classical result. Therefore, we will use these two approaches to investigate the Rutherford scattering and compare them by using the computed differential scattering cross sections.

FIG. 9: Classical differential cross section (in barns) versus the scattering angle (in radians) for the scattering of alpha particles travelling at 0.9c towards a gold nucleus.

FIG. 10: QFT differential cross section versus the scattering angle for the scattering of alpha particles travelling at 0.9c towards a gold nucleus.

In Fig. 9 we show the classical result for the scattering of alpha particles travelling at 0.9c towards a gold nucleus and Fig. 10 presents the QFT result for the same setting. In both models, we observe that the differential cross section is larger for smaller scattering angles, so the most part of the incident beam is not deflected (or very little) and a very small portion suffers large deflections. This makes sense as by increasing the impact parameter (and thus the cross section), the scattering angle goes to zero because the interaction between incident particles and nucleus weakens.

Hans Geiger and Ernest Marsden have found these circumstances in the gold foil experiments. They reported that most of alpha particles passed straight through the foil and some were deflected, with a tiny number of particles scattered at large angles that were not predicted by Thomson's plum pudding model. Hence, Ernest Rutherford proposed a more accurate model (equivalent to the approach of Classical Mechanics section) that overturned Thomson's model and explained large deflections as represented in Fig. 9.

FIG. 11: Classical differential cross section versus the atomic number for alpha particles at 0.9c scattered through 45°.

FIG. 12: QFT differential cross section versus the atomic number for alpha particles at $0.9c$ scattered through 45° .

Geiger and Marsden first used gold in their experiments because it is a malleable metal that can be beaten into very thin foils. In 1913, they also performed experiments using foils made from other metals (aluminum, copper, silver, and tin) to observe the material's effect on the scattering of alpha particles. The taken measurements showed that the scattering rate through a given angle increase for atoms with higher atomic numbers. This is consistent with both Classical results (represented in Fig. 11) and QFT results (represented in Fig. 12), as the Coulomb repulsion of alpha particles is stronger for nuclei with higher charges. Hence, gold is also useful because it makes the observation of the scattering events easier due to its atomic number, besides displaying small nucleus recoil as it is a heavy atom.

FIG. 13: Classical differential cross section versus the incident beam velocity relative to the speed of light for alpha particles scattered through 45° by a gold nucleus.

FIG. 14: QFT differential cross section versus the incident beam velocity relative to the speed of light for alpha particles scattered through 45° by a gold nucleus.

We show in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 the Classical and QFT results for the scattering of alpha particles through 45° related to the incident beam velocity. In both models, it is shown that the differential cross section is smaller for higher particle velocities. This is in agreement with the fact that faster particles experience the repulsion from the nucleus for less time, so they are more likely to pass through the gold atom without much deflection.

Hence, we have verified that the scattering angle, the atomic number, and the incident beam velocity are very relevant parameters that perform similar effects on both Classical and QFT approaches to the Rutherford scattering. However, observing the differential cross section values from the two models, the Classical results deviate from QFT results when the velocity of alpha particles are comparable to the speed of light. To reproduce these deviations, we show four figures that represent the two approaches to Rutherford scattering in ascending order of incident beam velocity: $0.5c$, $0.7c$, $0.9c$, $0.99c$.

FIG. 15: Classical and QFT results for the scattering of alpha particles travelling at $0.5c$ towards a gold nucleus.

FIG. 16: Classical and QFT results for the scattering of alpha particles travelling at $0.7c$ towards a gold nucleus.

FIG. 17: Classical and QFT results for the scattering of alpha particles travelling at $0.9c$ towards a gold nucleus.

FIG. 18: Classical and QFT results for the scattering of alpha particles travelling at $0.99c$ towards a gold nucleus.

The difference between Classical and QFT results clearly increase with the velocity as the relativistic effects play a more relevant role. The relativist mass correction is an effect that supports the deviations because

it is more difficult to deflect a faster particle as it is also "heavier". Thus, the QFT differential cross section is smaller than the Classical one, mostly for high incident beam velocities as represented in Fig. 19. We also verify that the ratio between Classical and QFT cross sections is higher for larger scattering angles as shown in Fig. 20.

FIG. 19: Ratio between Classical cross section and QFT cross section versus the velocity of alpha particles relative to the speed of light

FIG. 20: Ratio between Classical cross section and QFT cross section versus the scattering angle for two incident beam velocities.

Fig. 19 illustrates that both results are nearly identical when the velocity of alpha particles is much smaller than the speed of light. In the gold foil experiments, Geiger and Marsden used the decay of Radon-222 into Polonium-218 as the source of alpha particles, which have a typical energy of 5.5 MeV or a corresponding velocity of about $0.05c$. The relativistic effects are not relevant at this speed, so Rutherford's mathematical model was in line with Geiger-Marsden experiments. Hence, the Rutherford scattering is well described by the Classical result when the incident beam velocity is small compared to the speed of light, but the QFT result is more consistent when non-relativistic approximations are not accurate.

IV. CONCLUSION

The main idea of this study is to compare three different fields of Physics and analyze how they deal with the same problem. The Rutherford Scattering approaches were demonstrated and compared (quantitatively and qualitatively). The simulations support the results expected from the theories that the relativistic limits change the parameters - scattering angle and differential cross section.

We have verified that the theoretical results can explain the Geiger-Marsden observations on the scattering angle, atomic number, and incident beam velocity. We have shown that the velocities of the alpha particles in

the gold foil experiment were not sufficient to present large relativistic effects, hence the classical mathematical model developed by Rutherford was in good agreement with the experimental observations. However, the simulations confirm that the results would be very different if the projectiles were accelerated close to the speed of light, so a new approach arises - Quantum Field Theory.

In summation, we are better equipped to understand the actual components of physical phenomena as new theories advance throughout the years. Specifically, the latest approaches to Rutherford scattering introduce new parameters to the Classical Theory that describes more accurately the phenomenon - first quantum effects and then relativistic effects.

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